

1 **Farmers' knowledge and farm-level management practices of**
 2 **coconut pests in Ghana: Assessment based on gender differences.**

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16 **Abstract:** Coconut production is significantly constrained by agricultural pests. Given that
 17 management of these pests is influenced by gender differences, there was a need to assess
 18 farmers' knowledge about coconut pests, farm-level pest management strategies, and
 19 institutions offering training to farmers to develop an ecologically sound management
 20 strategy. To achieve this, we surveyed six coconut growing districts, three each from the
 21 Western and Central Regions of Ghana using face-to-face interviews, discussions, and direct
 22 observations. In addition, a multistage sampling technique was used to sample the coconut
 23 farmers. The sample population for each town was determined using a proportion to
 24 population size approach. The sample population was randomly drawn from each
 25 town/village using a sampling frame based on the agricultural sector records. Most of the
 26 farmers mentioned *Oryctes monoceros* as the most important pest of coconut. Significantly,
 27 more females than males mentioned weaver birds in their plantations ($p = 0.035$). Women
 28 who did not mention pests in their farms were significantly higher than men ($P = 0.007$). We
 29 observed a significant difference ($p = 0.018$) between male and female farmers who used
 30 indigenous knowledge (i.e., knowledge accumulated by an indigenous (local) population
 31 over generations of living in a certain area). However, pest management strategy did not
 32 vary in Central Region. Our findings showed that some of the farmers did not use any of
 33 the management strategies, suggesting that future studies and training are required to
 34 develop sustainable pest management strategies for the coconut pests.

35 **Keywords:** Coconut, pests, rodents, gender, coconut mites, weaver birds

36 1. Introduction

37 Coconut (*Cocos nucifera* Linnaeus) is a fibrous one-seeded drupe belonging to the palm
38 family Arecaceae which is widely distributed in the tropical and sub-tropical regions of the
39 world (Lims 2012; Niral and Jerard 2018). It provides food and income to the communities
40 involved in its production, processing, and marketing. The inner flesh of the mature nut and
41 the coconut milk derived from it is forms part of many people's diets. Coconut is rich in
42 manganese which is vital for bone health and metabolism of carbohydrates, proteins, and
43 cholesterol (Avila et al. 2013). Hundreds of millions of individuals drink coconut water and
44 consume kernel derivatives every day (Foale 2003). In most coconut farming communities,
45 one-third of the production is consumed fresh whereas 70% of the total production is
46 consumed domestically (FAO 2001). Over 80 million people directly depend on coconut
47 (FAO 2001). In 2018, global coconut production was 62 million tons, with 74% of the
48 production from Indonesia, the Philippines, and India (FAOSTAT 2018). In Ghana, coconut
49 and coconut-related activities provide employment (formal and informal) for over 700,000
50 people annually (Abankwah et al. 2010).

51

52 Globally, the total coconut cultivated area is about 12 million hectares, with which a
53 potential production of 70 billion nuts is estimated annually (Hoe 2018), highlighting the
54 crop's importance and leverage worldwide. In Ghana, for example, total coconut
55 production of 316,300 tons in 2008 was obtained from 55,000 ha, with an annual yield of

56 57,509 kg/ha (FAOSTAT 2018). Ten years later, the production increased to 394,883 tons
57 from 72,858 ha, with a yield of 54,199 kg/ha. Despite the rise in production, the yield has not
58 reached the global potential capabilities per year, and this has been associated with a myriad
59 of production constraints, with which arthropod pests are the economically most important
60 ones (Muyengi et al. 2015; Kadere 2021). Insect pests such as the Centaurus beetle *Augosoma*
61 *centaurus* Fabricius (Coleoptera: Scarabaeidae), Black ants, Coconut beetle *Oryctes monoceros*
62 Olivier (Coleoptera: Scarabaeidae), Red ants *Oecophylla longinoda* Latreille (Hymenoptera:
63 Formicidae), African palm weevil *Rynchophorus phoenicis* Fabricius (Coleoptera
64 Curculionidae), Termites (Blattodea: Termitidae) and the coreid bug *Pseudotheraptus*
65 *devastans* Distant (Heteroptera: Coreidae) have been reported as pests of coconut (Andoh-
66 Mensah et al. 2007). Other pests include Weaver birds *Ploceus cucullatus* Müller
67 (Passeriformes: Ploceidae) (DeGrazio 1978; Philippe and Dery 2004; Basheer and Aarif 2013)
68 and the coconut mites (The eriophyid coconut mite) *Aceria (Eriophyes) guerreronis* Keifer
69 (Acari: Trombidiformes) (Navia et al. 2013). These pests pose a severe threat to the coconut
70 industry, particularly in Ghana. Also, rodents (e.g., the greater cane rat (Grasscutter)
71 *Thryonomys swinderianus* Temminck (Rodentia: Thryonomyidae), and black rat (roof rat)
72 *Rattus rattus* L. (Rodentia: Muridae) are known pests of coconut (Geddes 1990). However,
73 information on the current coconut pest status and management strategies as reported by
74 men and women involved in coconut farming is poorly documented.

75

76 Different pest management strategies are often used by men and women based on their
77 gender roles, with men employing early planting to escape infestation, whereas women
78 spend their time in the field searching for pests and destroying them as they are responsible
79 for routine management (Kawarazuka et al. 2020). In coconut production, men are mainly
80 involved in land clearing, the application of pesticides and fertilizers, whereas women
81 perform in all other farm activities (Valleser et al. 2020). Anecdotal evidence suggests that
82 men and women are involved in coconut production to meet a wide range of demands, and
83 therefore preferences for pest management could vary by gender. Such variations in gender
84 towards pest management are critical for developing appropriate pest management
85 strategies (Erbaugh et al. 2003). In addition, pest management research and training
86 generally focus on “farmers,” ignoring gender perspectives (Kawarazuka et al. 2020).

87
88 In the present study, we sought to document the major coconut pest in Ghana, and assess
89 gender-based constraints and opportunities regulating farmers’ choices in managing
90 coconut pests. Specifically, we answered the question related to pests of coconut stated by
91 gender, management strategies used in solving pest problems, and whether institutional
92 training is influenced by gender. This information is essential for key stakeholders involved
93 in the promotion and/or dissemination of new technologies and improved coconut
94 cultivars.

95

96 2. Materials and Methods

97 Study design, setting and participants

98 We conducted a community-based cross-sectional study in 2020 in the Western and Central
99 Regions of Ghana (Figure 1), the major coconut-growing areas in Ghana (Caulum et al. 2012;
100 Okorley and Hazel 2004). Western Region has mean temperatures between 24 and 30°C,
101 with the lowest temperatures in August, whereas the highest temperatures occur between
102 March and April. The region has a bimodal rainfall pattern and lies within the moist
103 equatorial and semi-equatorial zones.

104
105 The annual rainfall in the region ranges from 1000mm to 2000mm. The wettest months are
106 between May and June, and September and October. The driest period occurs between
107 December and February. It has a short dry period in August. Fresh fruits and vegetables
108 have a high value in the region, making production in the area suitable. According to the
109 2020 census, the region has a total population of about 2 million, with 51.6% and 48.9% in
110 the urban and rural areas, respectively (Ghana Statistical Service 2021). The commonest
111 crops in the Western region are coconut, cocoa, cassava, and rubber. However, agriculture
112 is the largest industry and accounts for the highest proportion of employed persons in the
113 districts except for Sekondi-Takoradi. About 50% of all households in the region are
114 engaged in agriculture. The districts selected for sampling were Shama, Ellembelle, and
115 Ahanta West. Central Region has 57.9% and 42.1% urban and rural populations respectively

116 (Ghana Statistical Service 2021), with a total population of about 2.8 million. The population
117 of the region is almost equally divided between the sexes, but females marginally exceed
118 male populations. The mean temperature and average relative humidity are 31°C and 80%,
119 respectively. The wettest months are between May and June, and September and October,
120 whereas the driest months occur between November and March. It has a short dry period
121 in August. The most significant occupational groups (over 70%) in all the districts are
122 agricultural, forestry, and fishery workers. The study was conducted in three major coconut
123 production districts namely, Komenda-Edina-Eguafo-Abirem (KEEA), Abura-Asebu-
124 Kwamankese (AAK), and Agona East (AE).

125

126 **Sampling and data collection**

127 We used the sampling and data collection method described by Gesesew et al. (2016) with
128 some modifications. A multistage sampling technique was used to sample the coconut
129 farmers. Six major coconut growing districts were selected. From each district, towns that
130 are into coconut production were selected. The sample population for each town was
131 determined using a Proportion to Population Size method (PPS). The sample population
132 was drawn from each town using a simple random sampling utilizing a sampling frame
133 based on agricultural sector records. To obtain the aforementioned information, we planned
134 a face-to-face interview with the coconut farm owners. Also, data were collected through
135 discussions and direct observations due to weak infrastructure, little access to electronic

136 media, and low literacy levels of respondents in the rural areas. Before data collection,
137 twelve data collectors and four supervisors with prior survey expertise were trained on the
138 purpose and were abreast with the importance of data confidentiality, respondent rights,
139 and interview techniques. A standardized and pretested questionnaire was used for the
140 interview. The questionnaire was piloted among farmers in the area of the study, and any
141 necessary changes were made. The questionnaires were examined for validity by a team of
142 research experts from the Council for Scientific and Industrial Research's Coconut-Research
143 program and Science & Technology Policy Research Institute (STEPRI). Afterwards, the
144 questionnaires were translated to the native local languages (Fante and Nzema) spoken in
145 the districts to assist respondents who could not understand and speak the English
146 language. In some instances, a farmer was chosen as an interpreter who could speak and
147 explain further into the local language. Agricultural Extension Agents (AEAs) assigned by
148 the Ministry of Food and Agriculture (MoFA) to each location were randomly selected
149 based on their relationships with the surveyed farmers and prior knowledge about the
150 study area for easy administration of the questionnaires. Participants were interviewed in
151 the comfort of their own homes. We sampled 234 coconut farmers from Central (AAK: 70,
152 KEEA: 73 and Agona East: 91), and 230 from Western Regions (Shama: 77, Ellembelle: 64,
153 Ahanta west: 90).

154

155 The questionnaire had four main sections to answer questions related to; (i) Men and
156 women involved in coconut production demographic characteristics, (ii) their knowledge
157 towards the identification of pests' problems, (iii) farm-level management practices adopted
158 by different gender in solving pests' problems (iv) training received for coconut pests
159 management. The specific questions used for the data collection included; Farmer's age,
160 gender, level of education, size of farmer's farm in hectares, years of coconut farming
161 experience, years of formal schooling, any training in coconut farming, and which
162 organization/program provides such training. To collect data on pest problems, each farmer
163 was provided with a chart that has all the pests of coconut based on scientific literature
164 (DeGrazio 1978; Geddes 1990; Philippe Dery 2004; Andoh-Mensah et al. 2007; Basheer and
165 Aarif 2013; Navia et al. 2013). Farmers were asked if they have a pest problem, which type
166 of pest based on the pictorial chart, or if not included in the chart, the farmers were asked
167 to describe the pest based on the appearance and damage symptoms, and what
168 management strategies use to control the pests.

169

170 **Data Analysis**

171 Field data received from the field enumerators were regularly checked for quality to ensure
172 that the data collected met the relevant requirements. When the field survey was completed,
173 the data were entered in a Microsoft office excel format. The data were coded before
174 analysis. The datasets were exported to Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS)

175 version 27 (2020) for analysis. The calculation of percentages and means was done using
176 descriptive analysis. To compare the data by gender, we grouped the data based on farmer
177 age, experience, pests, farm size, education, and pest management strategies. We compared
178 the above parameters by gender using Z-test. The test was computed as;
179 where $z = z\text{-test}$, \bar{x} = sample average, μ_0 = mean, s = standard deviation.
180 All the analyses were tested at a 95% confidence level.

181

182 **3. Results**

183 **Demographic characteristics of the study population**

184 The demographic analysis showed that there was no significant difference between male
185 and female coconut farmers across the different age groups in the Central and Western
186 Regions ($p > 0.05$) (Figure 2a and b). In both regions, none of the farmers interviewed were
187 below 15 years. Our results showed that more males than females have had basic education,
188 whereas more females than males are without formal education in the two regions (Figure
189 2). Overall, the percentage of males who had basic education was significantly higher than
190 female farmers Central Region ($z = 2.23$, $p = 0.026$). Whereas significantly, more female than
191 male farmers had no formal education ($z = -3.79$, $p = 0.0001$) (Figure 2c). In the Western
192 Region, our results showed that the percentage of males who had basic education was
193 significantly higher than females ($z = 2.65$, $p = 0.008$), whereas significantly more females

194 had received other forms of education ($z = -4.91, p = 0.0001$). In addition, significantly, more
195 females than males had no formal education in the Western Region ($z = -2.60, p = 0.009$)
196 (Figure 2d).

197
198 In the Central and Western Regions, overall, there was no significant difference between the
199 year of farming experience and gender (Figure 3a and b). Similarly, our overall analysis
200 showed that farm size did not vary by gender in the Central Region (Figure 3c). Whereas,
201 in the Western Region, except for less than one hectare ($z = 2.23, p = 0.005$), all the farm sizes
202 did not significantly vary by gender (Figure 3d).

203
204 **Pests mentioned by coconut farmers**

205 In the Central and Western Regions, the pests mentioned by the coconut farmers are shown
206 in Figure 3. In the Central Region, a similar proportion of male and female farmers
207 mentioned all the pests ($p > 0.05$), except for weaver birds ($z = -2.40, p = 0.016$) (Figure 4a).
208 In the Western Region, significantly, more female than male did not mention any pest
209 incidence ($z = -2.83, p = 0.005$) (Figure 4b).

210
211 In all, significantly, more females than males mentioned weaver birds in their farms ($z = -$
212 $2.10, p = 0.035$). The results showed that more female than male coconut farmers did not
213 mention any pest problem ($z = -2.71, p = 0.007$) (Figure 5).

214 Farm-level insect pest management strategies

215 In the Central Region, the pest management strategy did not significantly vary by gender
216 in KEEA and AAK ($p > 0.05$) (Table 2a). However, in Agona East, more males than females
217 use chemical control for pest management. Moreover, a significant difference was observed
218 between female and male farmers who do not use any of the management approaches ($z =$
219 -2.34 , $p = 0.019$). In the Western Region, a similar proportion of male and female farmers use
220 different pest management strategies in all the districts except for Ahanta West (Table 1b).
221 In the Ahanta West district, we found that more males than females use integrated pest
222 management strategy.

223 4. Discussion

224 Coconut is an important crop that contributes to food security and the social life of some of
225 the world's poorest regions (Oyoo et al 2015; Gurr et al. 2016), but small-scale surveys of
226 coconut are scarce, particularly in terms of gender role in pest management. Our survey had
227 a broad scope and was conducted in two major coconut-producing regions, which covered
228 three main sections: 1) demographic features of the farmers, 2) pest problems, and 3) farm-
229 level management strategies. A majority of the sampled farmers were over 33 years, with
230 only a few farmers within the age bracket of 15-33yrs. These findings are consistent with
231 that of Okorley and Haizel (2004), who reported that most Ghanaian coconut farmers were
232 in the aging group, with more male than female farmers involved in its production in
233 Ghana.

234 The result from this study suggest that most of the female coconut farmers had no formal
235 education. But, had received more "other forms" of training such as vocational and
236 technical. This result agreed with that of Okorley and Haizel (2004), who found that women
237 in coconut production were less educated than men. It has been demonstrated that gender
238 and level of education can affect knowledge acquisition and farm-level decision-making,
239 and it should be fully understood if agricultural research and extension programs are to
240 design suitable technologies for small-scale farming systems (Erbaugh et al. 2003).

241 A previous study on maize in Ghana showed that resource availability was more important
242 in technology adoption decisions than gender (Doss and Morris 2000). Concerning coconut
243 farming experience, male and female farmers had a similar experience in the Western and
244 Central regions, suggesting that farmers could identify and adopt coconut farm-level pest
245 management strategies. This is particularly important for the coconut industry. For instance,
246 the level of awareness and knowledge of the stakeholders' pesticides is critical in adopting
247 new strategies aimed at preventing environmental and health risks associated with the
248 overuse of chemical pesticides. Moreover, Okorley and Haizel (2004), earlier reported that
249 most farmers interviewed had more than 10yrs of coconut farming experience, this is
250 consistent with our current study and may influence the adoption of agricultural
251 technologies. However, it is worth mentioning that farming experience is mainly useful for
252 specific crops in the early stages of implementing a given technology when farmers are still
253 checking their potential benefits (Ainembabazi and Mugisha 2014). We found that
254 significantly, more females than males owned coconut farmlands of less than 1 hectare.
255 Also, most of the farmers had farmlands of less than 1 hectare. Previous work showed that
256 land is a highly marketable commodity that provides input for food and most revenue-
257 generating activities, and plays a crucial role in socio-economic activities, particularly in
258 developing nations (Meinzen-Dick et al. 2019). Moreover women were usually involved in
259 food processing, food storage, transportation of produce, hoeing and weeding, harvesting,
260 and post-harvest care of produce, which is in agreement with the report of Drafor et al.

261 (2004). According to Okorley and Haizel (2004), women are involved in the marketing and
262 processing of coconut products rather than being directly involved in its cultivation.

263

264 Insect pests continue to be a pivotal setback to the coconut industry in Sub-Sahara Africa,
265 attacking crops leading to substantial economic losses (Philippe and Dery 2004; Pole et al.
266 2014). In all the study areas, most of the coconut farmers interviewed mentioned *O.*
267 *monoceros*, as a major constraint to coconut production which was also earlier reported as a
268 key pest of coconut in Ghana (Philippe and Dery 2004). Others include *E. guerreronis*, *A.*
269 *centaurus*, *T. swinderianus* *O. longinoda*, *R. phoenicis*, *P. cucullatus* Termites, and Black ants
270 (Andoh-Mensah et al. 2007; Nkansah-Poku et al. 2015). *O. monoceros* was a key pest stated
271 by the farmers in the two regions. Its activity inflicts physical damage to palms by boring
272 through the petiole bases and feeding on the succulent spear, leading to a fan-shape of
273 fronds and subsequent death of the emerged spear. Five to six beetles may attack the same
274 crown and feeding holes may serve as entry points for lethal secondary attacks by *R.*
275 *phoenicis* or other pathogens (Bedford 1980; Omotoso and Adedire 2008). For instance, in
276 Ivory Coast, damage up to 40% has been recorded (Allou et al. 2006). Currently,
277 management strategies of *O. monoceros* include the use of fishing nets, chemical pesticides,
278 chemical pesticides mixed with sawdust, and sharp metal hooks for the removal of adult

279 beetles (Philippe and Dery 2004). Insect pest damage affects its production and has been
280 associated with the loss of millions of palms annually (Allou et al. 2006).

281 Coconut mite (*E. guerreronis*) which was also mentioned by coconut farmers in both regions
282 is a serious pest of coconut worldwide (Howard et al. 1990; Fernando et al. 2003), and has
283 been associated with colossal economic losses (Aratchige et al. 2016). For instance, yield
284 losses in Benin were estimated at 10% (Nair et al. 2016), 16% in Ivory Coast (Julia and Mariau
285 1979), about 30% in Mexico (Navia et al. 2013), and up to 31.5% in St Lucia (Moore et al.
286 1989) and 2-3% in Sri Lanka (Wickramananda et al. 2007). In addition to insect pests and
287 coconut mites, the farmers stated birds and rodents as other coconut pests in Ghana.
288 Rodents that are also known to attack coconut include grasscutter (Caulum 2012) and bush
289 rat (MoFA 2015).

290 The farmers reported *O. longinoda* as a nuisance pests. An earlier study showed that *O.*
291 *longinoda* is generally recognized as a natural enemy but under heavy infestations they could
292 be recognized as a pest due to their nuisance during harvesting, weeding, and picking of
293 nuts after harvesting (Van Mele 2009).

294 Our results showed that more females than males used indigenous knowledge for pest
295 management, whereas more males than females use conventional pest management
296 strategies for coconut pest management. The differences in pest management by gender
297 could be attributed to expertise and participation in pest management strategies. The

298 findings may be associated with males who are mostly involved in the spraying of chemical
299 pesticides. This, however, confirms that male and female farmers play different roles in
300 agricultural production, and have different levels of expertise and participation in
301 managing pests (Kawarazuka et al. 2020; Valleser et al. 2020).

302 A crucial way of addressing pest problems is by preventing pest outbreaks (MoFA 2015;
303 Darfour and Rosentrater 2016), and understanding the role of gender in managing pests to
304 develop ecologically sound management technologies (Kawarazuka 2020). Hence, we have,
305 for the first time, assessed men and women's knowledge and farm-level management of
306 coconut pests to enhance our understanding in designing sustainable management
307 strategies for the pests, and manage them at a large scale. Also, behavioral variability
308 including the relationship between gender and pest management is a crucial problem for
309 understanding and predicting the effectiveness of the distribution of pest control
310 information throughout a community (Paredes et al. 2010).

311 The respondents indicated that the Ghanaian Ministry of Food and Agriculture (Agriculture
312 Extension service) was the central agency providing training for the farmers on coconut pest
313 management. The agriculture extension service support included technology transfer,
314 farmer training, farmer field schools, and input delivery distribution (Akotia 1999). The
315 ministry is in charge of agricultural production and growth in Ghana, with which its main
316 mission is to promote sustainable agriculture and productive agribusiness through the

317 development of science and technology, successful expansion, and other support services
318 for better livelihoods for farmers, processors, and traders (MoFA 2014).

319 Food insecurity continues to be a major challenge in Ghana, with about 5 percent of the
320 Ghanaian population (i.e., 1.2 million people) food insecure (Darfour and Rosentrater 2016).

321 An earlier observation noted that extension services focus on cash crops, typically owned
322 by men, thus the extension does not capture women (Akotia 1999). Men owned the cash
323 crop farms, women worked on them and cultivate food crops that were not covered by the
324 extension service. In combating rural poverty and food insecurity, agricultural extension
325 programs considering gender in their programs should be recognized as a key factor,
326 because it can transfer new technologies, encourage rural adult learning, help farmers solve
327 problems, and actively engage farmers in the knowledge and information system of
328 agriculture (Christoplos and Kidd 2000). Although men and women have a similar
329 agricultural position, they continue to have unequal access to resources (Anaglo et al. 2014),
330 as shown in the present study.

331 **5. Conclusions**

332 More men than women cultivate coconut in Ghana. However, male farmers own larger
333 farms than females. Women were less educated than men which could affect their adoption
334 of agriculture technologies. The farmers have prior knowledge of coconut production to
335 receive and adopt new pest management technologies. The key pest of coconut is *O.*

336 *monoceros*. The farmers use integrated, conventional, and indigenous knowledge for pest
337 management, but some of the farmers do not use any of the management strategies. More
338 females than males did not use any pest management strategy in the Central Region. Pest
339 management strategy did not vary in Central Region but varied in the Western region.

340
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359

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- 494

495 **Table 1a. Practices used by farmers who controlled insect pests on coconut in Central Region in Ghana**

Insect pests control method	Central Region											
	Number of farmers											
	KEEA (%)				AAK (%)				Agona East (%)			
	Male	Female	z-value	<i>p-value</i>	Male	Female	z-value	<i>p-value</i>	Male	Female	z-value	<i>p-value</i>
Conventional (chemical control) pest management	20.37	21.05	-0.06	0.950	37.88	20	0.80	0.424	45.68	9.09	2.31	0.021
Indigenous knowledge pest management	12.96	26.32	-1.35	0.177	9.09	0	0.70	0.481	13.58	27.27	-1.19	0.236
Integrated pest management (chemical, cultural, physical control)	38.89	21.05	1.41	0.159	24.24	20	0.21	0.830	12.35	0	1.23	0.217
None	27.78	31.58	-0.31	0.753	25.76	60	-1.64	0.101	28.4	63.64	-2.34	0.019

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502 **Table 1b. Practices used by farmers who controlled insect pests on coconut in Western Region in Ghana**

Insect pests control method	Western Region											
	Number of farmers											
	Shama (%)				Ellembelle (%)				Ahanta West (%)			
	Male	Female	z-value	<i>p-value</i>	Male	Female	z-value	<i>p-value</i>	Male	Female	z-value	<i>p-value</i>
Conventional (chemical control) pest management	17.74	26.67	-0.62	0.533	44.9	46.67	-0.12	0.904	39.13	61.9	-1.84	0.066
Indigenous knowledge pest management	8.06	13.33	-0.45	0.655	8.16	20	-1.29	0.199	10.14	19.05	-1.09	0.275
Integrated pest management (chemical, cultural and physical control)	58.06	40	1.26	0.207	28.57	20	0.66	0.511	31.88	9.52	2.03	0.042
None	4.84	6.67	-0.19	0.846	18.37	13.33	0.45	0.651	1.45	0	0.55	0.579

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507 **Figure legends (Caption)**

508 Figure 1. Map representing the six study districts in two main coconut regions of Ghana.
 509 Green colour represents districts sampled in the Western Region, orange represents districts
 510 sampled in the Central Region of Ghana.

511
 512 Figure 2. Percentage of coconut farmers' age by gender in the Central Region (a) and
 513 Western Region (b), and percentage of farmer's educational level by gender in the Central
 514 Region (c) and Western Region (d) Western Region. Bars with "ns" are not significant,
 515 whereas "*" indicates a significant difference for male and female respondents, $p < 0.05$,
 516 two-proportion z-test.

517
 518 Figure 3. Percentage of coconut farming experience by gender in the Central Region (a) and
 519 Western Region (b), and percentage of farmer farm size by gender in the Central Region (c)
 520 and Western Region (d) Western Region. Bars with "ns" are not significant, whereas "*" indicates significant differences for male and female respondents, $p < 0.05$, two-proportion
 521 z-test.
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523
 524 Figure 4. Percentage of pests mentioned by gender in the Central Region (a) and Western
 525 Region (b). Bars with "ns" are not significant, whereas "*" indicates a significant difference
 526 for male and female respondents, $P < 0.05$, two-proportion z-test. *Augosoma centaurus* (AC),
 527 Black ants (BA), *Thryonomys swinderianus* (GC), *Eriophyes guerreronis* (CM), *Oryctes monoceros*
 528 (CB), *Oecophylla longinoda* (RA), *Rynchophorus phoenicis* (APW), Termites (TM), *Ploceus*
 529 *cucullatus* (WB), None.

530
 531 Figure 5. The overall percentage of pests is shown by gender in the Central Region and
 532 Western Regions. Bars with "ns" are not significant, whereas "*" indicates a significant
 533 difference for male and female respondents, $P < 0.05$, two-proportion z-test. *Augosoma*
 534 *centaurus* (AC), Black ants (BA), *Thryonomys swinderianus*(GC), *Eriophyes guerreronis* (CM),
 535 *Oryctes monoceros* (CB), *Oecophylla longinoda* (RA), *Rynchophorus phoenicis* (APW), Termites
 536 (TM), *Ploceus cucullatus* (WB), None.

Figure 1.

Figure 2.

Figure 3.

Figure 4.

Figure 5.